

Synthesis and Utilisation of Chiral 3-*N*-Benzyl-*N*-methylaminoperhydropyrrolo-[2,1-*c*][1,4]oxazin-4-one as a Novel Precursor for the Enantioselective Synthesis of α -Amino Acids and Their *N*-Methyl Derivatives[†]

GANESH PANDEY* and PARTHASARATHI DAS

Division of Organic Chemistry (Synthesis), National Chemical Laboratory, Pune-411 008

Manuscript received 31 July 1998

α -Amino acids and their *N*-methyl derivatives are synthesised in good optical purity by the nucleophilic alkylation of chiral 3-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylaminoperhydropyrrolo[2,1-*c*][1,4]oxazin-4-one (1). The chiral auxiliary, L-prolinol, is isolated in recyclable form.

Due to central role played by α -amino acids in chemistry and biology, the development of versatile and new methodology for the synthesis of natural and non-natural amino acids, in optically active form has emerged as an important and challenging synthetic endeavour for organic chemists¹. Similarly, the preparation of *N*-methyl-L-amino acids has also been attracting considerable attention recently² owing to their use as building blocks for many peptides and depsipeptides antibiotics³. Among the various methodologies for α -amino acids synthesis, alkylation of several glycine derived chiral templates has served as an important approach⁴. However, the problem associated with the cleavage of the auxiliary ring system, recovery of chiral information and the difficulty in extending these strategies for the synthesis of *N*-methylamino acids led us to explore an alternative strategy. In this context, we have designed substrate 1 as an ideal precursor for the synthesis of various α -amino acids as well as their *N*-methyl derivatives.

The designing of 1 is done by considering its unique structural features such as a reactive α -amino ether moiety; highly suitable for stereoselective nucleophilic alkylation reaction, easy hydrolysability of the resultant amide 2 to procure corresponding α -amino acids 3, recovery of the prolinol (4) chiral auxiliary (Scheme 1) and the opportunity of manipulating amine functionality of 3 to incorporate different substituents. We disclose herein full details⁵ of our effort in this artical.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis of precursor compound 1 was envisioned,

Scheme 1

as shown retrosynthetically in Scheme 2, through an intramolecular cyclisation of an *in situ* generated iminium cation intermediate 5 by PET initiation of 6, a well established strategy from our group⁶. Compound 6 was obtained by the

Scheme 2. Reagents : (a) $h\nu$, DCN, MV^{++} , CH_3CN , 8 h (73%).

amination of compound 8, derived by the reaction of 7 with chloroacetyl chloride, with benzylmethylamine, using K_2CO_3 as a base in acetonitrile followed by the reduction of 9 with $NaBH_4$ (Scheme 3). The generation of iminium

Scheme 3

cation intermediate 5 involved sequential two-electron oxidation of 6 by PET reaction using 1,4-dicyanonaphthalene (DCN) as an electron acceptor and methyl viologen (MV^{++}) as an electron relay by following the mechanism as shown in Scheme 4.

The PET initiation involved irradiation of a mixture containing mixtures of 6 (2 g, 7.69 mmol), 1,4-dicyanonaphthalene (DCN; 0.32 g, 1.79 mmol) and methyl viologen

[†] Dedicated with respect to Dr. Sukh Dev, an outstanding organic chemist of the country, on the occasion of his 75th. birthday.

Scheme 4

(MV⁺⁺) (0.08 g, 0.311 mmol) in dry CH₃CN using pyrex filtered light (>280 nm) emanating from a 450-W Hanovia medium pressure mercury lamp at ambient temperature without removing dissolved air present in the solution. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc and hplc. Photolysis was discontinued after 8 h. The removal of the solvent under reduced pressure followed by chromatographic purification of the crude mixture gave **1** (73%) as a mixture of diastereomeric mixture (de = 93%). Our effort to purify pure diastereomers, however, failed.

The formation of **1** as major diastereomer in this photoreaction may be explained by considering the regioselective *in situ* generation of iminium cation **5** by selective deprotonation from the acidic methylene group of the glycine moiety from the PET generated amine radical cation followed by further one-electron transfer to DCN. The diastereomeric ratio of **1** (13.3 : 1) was established by hplc analysis. The stereochemistry of the major isomer, purified by careful chromatography, was determined by comparing the relatively high field ¹³C and ¹H nmr chemical shifts values for C-3 and H-3 respectively, with minor isomer⁷ which was confirmed by the absence of NOE between H-3 and H-8a. The preference for the formation of major diastereomer **1** may be explained by assuming the backside attack of OH moiety of prolinol to a preferred energy minimised transition state encompassing iminium cation where amine functionality remains at the equatorial position C in order to produce less energetic *trans*-bicyclic system, as shown in Scheme 5.

Scheme 5

The high reactivity profile of the α -amino ether chiral center (masked iminium cation equivalent) of **1** gave us an opportunity to exploit it for stereoselective nucleophilic alky-

			Yield% (isolated)
i = -Ph	74	26	70
ii = -Me	80	20	72
iii = -CH ₂ Ph	84	16	76
iv = -CH(Me) ₂	76	24	68

Scheme 6

lation reactions⁸. Nucleophilic ring opening of **1** (Scheme 6) at first was achieved by the addition of a separately prepared Grignard reagent (4 equivalent) to a stirred solution of **1** (0.5 g, 1.93 mmol) in dry ether at -50° for 4 h and allowing the stirring to continue for another 2 h. Usual workup and purification gave the corresponding amides (**10-13-a**) and (**10-13-b**) in 70–75% yields. The diastereomeric ratios of (**10-13-a**) and (**10-13-b**) are shown in Scheme 6. These products were characterized by ir, ¹H, ¹³C nmr and mass spectral data. The diastereomeric ratios of (**10-13-a**)/(**10-13-b**) were determined by comparing the area ratio of *N*-methyl peaks in ¹H nmr spectra and were further confirmed by analysing them by hplc. Due to close R_f values between (**10-13-a**) and (**10-13-b**) we failed to isolate them in pure form. Thus, the hydrolysis of the diastereomeric mixtures of (**10-13-a**) and (**10-13-b**) was carried out as such. This was achieved by heating amides in dry methanolic HCl for 12 h in a sealed tube. The usual workup, basification and purification, gave the corresponding esters of α -amino acids in 60–70% yield. L-Prolinol, the chiral auxiliary, was recovered in 96% yield (Scheme 7). The absolute configu-

Scheme 7

Scheme 8

ration of the esters of α -amino acids were determined by comparing their optical rotations with the authentic samples prepared independently from the commercially available α -amino acids. Debenzylation achieved by the hydrogenation over 10% Pd-charcoal gave the corresponding *N*-methyl- α -amino acid esters. Free amino acids or esters may also be obtained by the *N*-demethylation of debenzylated product using known procedures⁹.

In order to explore an alternative approach for the alkylation reaction, Lewis acid mediated alkylation^{10,11} of **1** was also carried out. The addition of allyltrimethylsilane (0.32 g, 2.8 mmol) to a stirred solution of **1** (0.50 g, 1.93 mmol) in dry DCM at -78° followed by the addition of TiCl_4 (0.546 g, 2.88 mmol) for 4 h gave **15a** and **15b** (90% yield) in 9 : 1 ratio (Scheme 8).

The absolute stereochemistry of allylated product was determined after hydrogenation of the allylic bond using 10% Pd/C, followed by hydrolysing the resultant amide as described earlier (Scheme 7) and by comparing the optical rotation of the esters of the corresponding amino acid with the authentic sample prepared independently from the commercially available α -amino acid.

In conclusion, we have developed a new glycine derived chiral template, based on a recyclable chiral L-prolinol auxiliary, for the synthesis of α -amino acids and their *N*-methyl derivatives in good optical purity.

Experimental

The chemicals and reagents used were of commercial grade pure and some of them were used after purification. Methyl viologen dichloride hydrate (Aldrich) was used as such. Dicyanonaphthalene (DCN) was prepared by the standard procedure. The chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). The solvents used during experiments were purified, unless otherwise stated, by standard literature procedure.

All new compounds were characterised by ir, ^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr, and mass spectroscopy. ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded on a Bruker AC (200 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal reference, ir spectra on Perkin-Elmer 599-B instrument and mode 11620 FT-IR and mass spectra on a Finnigan-Mat 1020C spectrometer at an ionisation potential of 70 eV. Hplc was performed on reverse phase nucleosil[®] 5C₁₈ column using water and acetonitrile as eluents. Optical rotations were measured at the sodium D line on a JASCO-181 polarimeter at ambient temperature. Equipment used for photolysis were 450-W Hanovia medium pressure mercury lamp, Pyrex filtered immersion well and reaction vessels, all from ACE Glass, USA.

N-Chloroacetyl-S(-)-methyl prolineate (**8**): To a stirred

solution of L-proline methyl ester (10 g, 81.79 mmol) and ice-water (150 ml), NaHCO_3 (13.73 g, 163.47 mmol) was added. After dissolution of NaHCO_3 , chloroacetyl chloride (13.12 g, 116.16 mmol) was added dropwise over a period of 15 min and stirring was allowed for further 1 h at 0° . The reaction mixture was then neutralised with 10% HCl solution and extracted with chloroform (2×50 ml). The combined organic extracts was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated under reduced pressure to give **8** (15.61 g, 98%): ν_{max} 2950, 1735, 1645, 1140, 1080 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 2.10–2.40 (4H, m), 3.60–3.70 (2H, m), 3.75 (3H, s), 4.10 (2H, s), 4.55–4.60 (1H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 24.82, 29.23, 42.46, 47.68, 52.47, 59.36, 165.55, 172.12; m/z 205 (M^+), 146 (51), 70 (100).

N-Benzyl-*N*-methylglycyl-S(-)-methyl prolineate (**9**): To a stirred solution (100 ml) of **8** (9.5 g, 46.19 mmol) in dry acetonitrile under argon gas, K_2CO_3 (7.66 g, 55.43 mmol) was added. After 10 min, benzylmethylamine (6.7 g, 55.42 mmol) was added dropwise over a period of 10 min and the mixture was stirred at room temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. After completion of the reaction (6 h), the reaction mixture was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude reaction mixture was purified by column chromatography using acetone : petroleum ether (1 : 4) as eluents to give **9** (12.3 g, 94%) as a viscous liquid: ν_{max} (neat) 3020, 2990, 1730, 1640, 1495, 1065 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.90–2.35 (2H, m), 2.40 (3H, s), 3.10–3.20 (2H, dd, J_1 9.8 Hz, J_2 5.2 Hz), 3.40–3.45 (2H, m), 3.55–3.65 (4H, m), 3.75 (3H, s), 4.55 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 25.00, 28.94, 42.39, 46.80, 52.04, 58.78, 60.06, 61.75, 127.11, 128.18, 129.24, 138.46, 169.23, 172.73.

N-Benzyl-*N*-methylglycyl-S(-)-prolinol (**6**): To an ethanolic solution (120 ml) of **9** (11.2 g, 38.62 mmol), sodium borohydride (2.19 g, 57.93 mmol) was added in portions while stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred at RT (12 h). It was then concentrated and washed with 40% NaHCO_3 solution. The aqueous layer was extracted with ethyl acetate (4×25 ml) and washed with brine. The combined organic layers was concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude reaction mixture was purified through column chromatography using acetone : petroleum ether (2 : 3) as eluents to give **6** (8.33 g, 84%) as a viscous liquid: ν_{max} (neat) 3400, 3000, 2924, 1640, 1495, 1069 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.45–1.55 (1H, m), 1.80–1.95 (3H, m), 2.40 (3H, s), 3.15 (2H, s), 3.30–3.35 (2H, m), 3.60–3.70 (4H, m), 4.15–4.20 (1H, m), 7.25–7.30 (5H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 24.14, 27.54, 42.39, 47.17, 60.04, 60.68, 61.67, 65.80, 126.96, 127.99, 128.94, 138.05, 170.80; m/z 262 (M^+), 134 (100), 133 (76), 120

(41), 91 (79).

PET activation of N-benzyl-N-methylglycyl-S(-)prolinol : A solution containing **6** (2 g, 7.69 mmol), DCN (0.38 g, 1.79 mmol) and MV⁺⁺ (0.088 g, 0.311 mmol) in acetonitrile (1.8 dm³) was irradiated by using 450-W Hanovia medium pressure mercury vapour lamp in pyrex filtered immersion jacket for 8 h. During the course of irradiation, the colour of the solution changed to blue initially and then dark which finally turned to pale yellow. Progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc (acetone : petroleum 30 : 70) and hplc. After the disappearance of starting material (74%) irradiation was discontinued. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and purification of the crude photolysate through column chromatography using acetone : petroleum ether as eluents gave **1** (1.6 g, 72%) as a mixture of two diastereomers (de = 93%) (DCN was recovered back in 99% yield) : ν_{\max} (neat) 3000, 2930, 1680, 1450, 1180 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.30–1.35 (1H, m), 1.90–2.00 (3H, m), 2.25–2.30 (1H, m), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.45 (3H, s), 3.30 (1H, t, *J* 9.2 Hz), 3.65–3.80 (4H, m), 4.2 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 9.6 Hz, *J*₂ 5.1 Hz), 4.75 (1H, s), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m); ¹³C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 22.78, 29.03, 37.18, 45.42, 57.08, 57.62, 67.42, 91.26, 127.19, 128.33, 129.20, 138.85, 165.93; *m/z* 260 (M⁺), 149 (15), 135 (100), 134 (73), 120 (40), 106 (32), 105 (29), 91 (57).

General alkylation procedure of 1 using Grignard reagents : This is illustrated by taking the example of synthesis of *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylphenylglycyl-S(-)-prolinol (**10a** and **10b**). To a stirred solution of **1** (0.5 g, 1.93 mmol) in dry ether (20 ml) cooled to -50° and under argon gas, phenyl magnesium bromide [prepared freshly from magnesium (0.187 g, 7.72 mmol) and bromo benzene (1.2 g, 7.72 mmol) in 10 ml ether] was added slowly. The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 h at -50°, then allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred for another 2 h. The reaction was quenched with saturated ammonium chloride solution (5 ml). Aqueous layer was extracted with ether (3×20 ml), washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Concentration under reduced pressure followed by purification by silica gel column chromatography using acetone : petroleum ether (2 : 8) as eluents gave **10a** and **10b** (74 : 26) (0.453 g, 70%) as a clear liquid. The diastereomeric ratio was determined by measuring the area ratio of *N*-methyl peaks in ¹H nmr spectra and was further confirmed by hplc using C₁₈ column and acetonitrile water as eluents : ν_{\max} (neat) 3400, 3000, 2980, 1675, 1440, 1190 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.5–1.60 (1H, m), 1.65–2.00 (4H, m), 2.40 (3H, s), 3.30–3.35 (1H, m), 3.60–3.85 (5H, m), 4.20 (1H, m), 4.55 (1H, s), 7.30–7.35 (10H, m); ¹³C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 24.58, 28.11, 39.42, 47.66, 58.51, 61.71, 67.69, 69.78,

127.16, 128.24, 128.39, 128.81, 129.12, 129.41, 129.58, 139.38, 139.70, 173.37; *m/z* 338 (M⁺), 224 (75), 210 (82), 118 (18), 105 (22), 91 (100), 77 (21).

Similar procedure was adopted with other Grignard reagents and the details as follows : *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylalanyl-S(-)-prolinol (**11a** and **11b**), yield 72%, dr = 3.6 : 1, ν_{\max} (neat) 3500, 2995, 1670, 1425, 1170, 1080 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.25 (3H, t, *J* 6.2 Hz), 1.50–1.55 (1H, m), 1.60–2.10 (4H, m), 2.25 (3H, s), 2.30 (3H, s), 3.30–3.35 (1H, m), 3.55–3.70 (4H, m), 4.05–4.15 (1H, m), 4.20–4.25 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m), ¹³C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 8.93, 24.17, 27.51, 37.29, 47.43, 57.43, 59.70, 60.51, 65.93, 126.75, 127.94, 128.65, 138.92, 173.51, *m/z* 276 (M⁺), 192 (46), 148 (32), 91 (100); *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylphenylalanyl-S(-)-prolinol (**12a** and **12b**), yield 76% dr = 5.1 : 1, ν_{\max} (neat) 3450, 3020, 2990, 1685, 1460, 1180 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.35–1.45 (1H, m), 1.60–1.70 (2H, m), 1.80–2.00 (2H, m), 2.40 (3H, s), 2.65–2.70 (1H, m), 2.90–3.05 (1H, dd, *J*₁ 12.8 Hz, *J*₂ 5.8 Hz), 3.30–3.40 (3H, m), 3.60–3.65 (2H, dd *J*₁ 9.4 Hz, *J*₂ 4.8 Hz), 3.75 (2H, s), 4.20–4.25 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (10H, m), ¹³C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 24.42, 28.28, 32.84, 38.90, 47.35, 58.42, 61.34, 66.60, 66.95, 126.46, 127.25, 128.43, 128.53, 128.91, 129.54, 138.98, 139.46, 172.62, *m/z* 352 (M⁺), 261 (11), 224 (96), 91 (100); *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylvalinyl-S(-)-prolinol (**13a** and **13b**), yield 68%, dr = 3.2 : 1, ν_{\max} (neat) 3500, 2995, 1670, 1425, 1170, 1080 cm⁻¹, ¹H nmr (200 MHz) δ 0.85–0.90 (3H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 0.95–1.00 (3H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 1.10–1.15 (3H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 1.55–1.60 (1H, m), 1.85–1.95 (3H, m), 2.25–2.30 (1H, m), 2.35 (3H, s), 3.15–3.20 (1H, t, *J* 9.2 Hz), 3.50–3.80 (5H, m), 3.95–4.00 (1H, d, *J* 5.8 Hz), 4.35–4.45 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m), ¹³C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 19.65, 19.89, 24.53, 28.16, 28.57, 38.51, 47.89, 57.84, 60.71, 67.38, 70.11, 126.70, 128.15, 129.20, 140.02, 173.82, *m/z* 304 (M⁺), 261 (12), 176 (100), 91 (81).

***N*-Benzyl-*N*-methylallylglycyl-S(-)-prolinol (**15a** and **15b**)** : To a stirred solution of **1** (0.5 g, 1.93 mmol) in dry DCM (20 ml) cooled to -78° and under argon gas, allyltrimethylsilane (0.32 g, 2.28 mmol) followed by TiCl₄ (0.54 g, 2.88 mmol) were added slowly. After stirring for 4 h at -78°, the mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and quenched with saturated ammonium chloride solution (5 ml). After basification with sodium bicarbonate solution, it was extracted with DCM (3×25 ml), washed with brine solution and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Concentration under reduced pressure followed by purification over silica gel column using acetone : petroleum ether (2 : 8) as eluents gave **15a** and **15b** (19 : 10) (0.52 g, 90%) as a clear liquid : ν_{\max} (neat) 3460, 2995,

1680, 1425, 1340, 1180 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.45–2.10 (4H, m), 2.30 (3H, s), 2.42–2.50 (1H, m), 2.65–2.75 (1H, m), 3.20–3.70 (7H, m), 4.20–4.30 (1H, m), 4.95–5.20 (2H, m), 5.65–5.75 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 24.59, 28.19, 29.96, 38.37, 47.87, 58.02, 61.14, 64.89, 67.30, 117.25, 127.20, 128.39, 128.98, 135.13, 139.28, 172.98; m/z 302 (M^+), 261 (10), 174 (100), 91 (60).

General method for hydrolysis of resultant amides (10-13-a) and (10-13-b) : This is illustrated by taking the hydrolysis of *N*-benzyl-*N*-methylphenylglycyl-*S*(-)-prolinol (10a and 10b) as an example. Compound 10 (a, b) (0.45 g, 1.33 mmol) was dissolved in dry methanolic HCl (6 *N*; 15 ml) and transferred into a narrow-neck test tube. The tube was sealed and heated to 65° for 24 h in an oil-bath. The sealed tube was cooled to room temperature and opened by scissoring the tip. The methanolic HCl was evaporated to dryness and the resulting viscous residue was basified with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution (pH 8). The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (4×20 ml). Combined organic extracts was washed with brine and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Concentration followed by purification of crude reaction mixture through silica gel column, using ethylacetate : petroleum ether (1 : 12) mixture as eluent, gave (*S*)(+)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylphenylglycinemethyl ester (16; 0.22 g, 70%) as a clear liquid, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ authentic +11.9 ($c = 1.2$, CHCl_3), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ obs +5.86 ($c = 1$, CHCl_3); ν_{max} (neat) 3020, 2980, 1735, 1440, 1210, 1160 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 2.30 (3H, s), 3.10–3.20 (2H, q, J 13.8 Hz), 3.70 (3H, s), 4.40 (1H, s), 7.25–7.45 (10H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 39.04, 51.51, 58.60, 72.09, 127.03, 128.15, 128.24, 128.50, 128.81, 136.74, 138.98, 172.16; m/z 269 (M^+), 224 (10), 210 (60), 176 (12), 91 (100).

Similar procedure was adopted to obtain other corresponding amino acid esters : *S*(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylalanine methyl ester (17), yield 72%, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ authentic -99.11 ($c = 1.2$, CHCl_3), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ obs -59.36 ($c = 1$, CHCl_3), ν_{max} (neat) 3000, 2980, 1730, 1425, 1230, 1140 cm^{-1} , ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 1.35–1.40 (3H, d, J 7.3 Hz), 2.35 (3H, s), 3.45–3.55 (2H, q, J 7.8 Hz), 3.60–3.75 (1H, q, J 9.2 Hz), 3.75 (3H, s), 7.25–7.35 (5H, m), ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 14.87, 37.82, 51.05, 58.35, 60.62, 126.95, 128.22, 128.71, 139.41, 173.64, m/z 207 (M^+), 192 (12), 176 (21), 105 (10), 91 (100); *S*(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylphenylalanine methyl ester (18), yield 72%, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ authentic -73.59 ($c = 1.4$, CHCl_3), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ obs -51.23 ($c = 1$, CHCl_3), ν_{max} (neat) 3010, 2990, 1735, 1430, 1210, 1140, 1080 cm^{-1} , ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 2.40 (3H, s), 3.30–3.20 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 3.65–3.90 (6H, m), 7.30–7.35 (10H, m), ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 36.00, 38.05, 51.10, 59.07, 67.46, 126.45, 127.10,

128.33, 128.41, 128.82, 129.40, 138.65, 139.39, 172.43, m/z 283 (M^+), 224 (42), 192 (53), 91 (100), 77 (38); *S*(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylvaline methyl ester (19), yield 70%, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ authentic -68.12 ($c = 1.36$, CHCl_3), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ obs -32.89 ($c = 1.2$, CHCl_3), ν_{max} (neat) 2990, 2925, 1735, 1450, 1230, 1080 cm^{-1} , ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 0.85–0.95 (3H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 1.10–1.15 (3H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 2.10–2.20 (1H, m), 2.30 (3H, s), 2.90–2.95 (1H, d, J 6.8 Hz) 3.55–3.60 (1H, d, J 10.2 Hz), 3.75–3.95 (4H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m), ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 19.50, 20.01, 27.53, 37.84, 50.52, 58.79, 73.11, 126.97, 128.30, 128.65, 139.76, 172.23, m/z 235 (M^+), 192 (15), 176 (58), 91 (100), 44 (60); *S*(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylallylglycinemethylester (20), yield 76%, ν_{max} (neat) 2995, 1735, 1425, 1340, 1180 cm^{-1} , ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 2.30 (3H, s), 2.50–2.55 (2H, m), 3.40–3.50 (1H, t, J 6.6 Hz), 3.60–3.80 (5H, m), 5.15–5.20 (2H, m), 5.85–5.90 (1H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m), ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 34.24, 38.07, 51.09, 58.64, 65.86, 117.06, 127.12, 128.37, 128.86, 135.00, 139.52, 172.56, m/z 233 (M^+), 192 (49), 174 (43), 91 (100), 77 (39).

S(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylnorvalinemethylester (21) : To a stirred solution of 20 (0.23 g, 0.98 mmol) in ethanol (25 ml) activated paladium-charcol (10%) was added, and the mixture was saturated with atmospheric pressure of hydrogen and stirred for 12 h at room temperature. After filtration through celite, the reaction mixture was concentrated and purified by silica gel column chromatography using ethyl acetate : petroleum ether (1 : 12) as eluents to give *S*(-)-*N*-benzyl-*N*-methylnorvaline methyl ester (0.20 g, 90%) as viscous liquid : $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ authentic -76.38 ($c = 1.2$, CHCl_3), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ obs -62.23 ($c = 1$, CHCl_3); ν_{max} (neat) 3000, 1730, 1425, 1230, 1140 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (200 MHz) δ 0.85–0.95 (3H, t, J 6.2 Hz), 1.40–1.50 (2H, m), 1.70–1.75 (2H, m), 2.30 (3H, s), 3.30–3.35 (1H, t, J 7.2 Hz) 3.60–3.85 (5H, m), 7.30–7.35 (5H, m); ^{13}C nmr (50.32 MHz) δ 14.09, 19.72, 32.09, 37.94, 37.94, 51.00, 58.78, 65.62, 127.14, 128.44, 128.90, 139.93, 173.46; m/z 235 (M^+), 176 (92), 91 (100).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.S.D.) thank C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

References

1. M. J. O'DONNELL, *Tetrahedron Symposia-in-print*, 1988, **44**, 5253; R. M. WILLIAMS, "Organic Chemistry Series : Synthesis of Optically Active α -Amino Acids", eds. J. E. BALDWIN and P. D. MAGNUS, Pergamon, Oxford, 1989, Vol. 7; J. JURCZAK and A. GOLEBIOWSKI, *Chem. Rev.*, 1989, **89**, 149; R. O. DUTHALER, *Tetrahedron*, 1994, **50**, 1539.
2. For recent synthetic approaches for the preparation of *N*-methyl-L-amino acids see : U. GROGER, K. DRAUZ and H. KLENK,

- Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1992, 195; C -B. XUE and W. F. DEGRADO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, 36, 55 and references cited therein.
3. H KLEINKAUF and H. VON DOHREN, in "Regulation of Secondary Metabolic Formation", eds. H. KLEINKAUF and H VON DOHREN, H. DORNAUER and G. NESEMANN, VCH, Weinheim, 1996, pp. 173-207, and references cited therein, R. H. MAZUR, P. A. JAMES, D. A. TYNER, E. A. HALLINAN, J. H. SANNER and R. SCHULZE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1980, 23, 785, and references cited therein.
 4. W. OPPOLZER, R. MORETTI and C. ZHOU, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1994, 77, 2363, and references cited therein.
 5. G. PANDEY, P. Y. REDDY and P. DAS, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, 37, 3175.
 6. G. PANDEY, G. KUMARSWAMY and P. Y. REDDY, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, 48, 8295; G. PANDEY, P. Y. REDDY and U. T. BHALERAO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, 32, 5147
 7. D. A. BURNETT, J. K. CHOI, D. J. HART and Y. M. TSAI, *A. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 106, 8201.
 8. M. J. WU and L. N. PRIDGEN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1991, 56, 1340; A. ALBEROLA, C. ANDRES and R. PEDROSA, *Synlett*, 1990, 763.
 9. R. A. OLOFSON, T. J. MARTZ, J. P. SENET, M. PITEAU and T. MALFROOT, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, 49, 2081.
 10. M. T. REETZ, KESSERLER, S. SCHMIDTBERGER, B. WENDERROTH and R. STEINBACH, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1983, 989.
 11. W. C. STILL and J. H. MCDONALD, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, 21, 1031; W. C. STILL and J. A. SCHNEIDER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, 21, 1035.